

STUDENT DROP-OUTS: REASONS AND EXPERIENCES IN ELEMENTARY, HIGH SCHOOL AND COLLEGE

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to discuss the reasons for and experiences of students who dropped out of elementary, high school and college from 2014 to 17 at Jose Rizal University in Mandaluyong City, Philippines. A descriptive cross-sectional study was utilized, employing review of exit interview forms from elementary, high school and college during the academic years 2014-15, 2015-16 and 2016-17. Data included the reasons as well as positive and negative experiences of students who dropped out. It was found that top reasons for dropping out were: change of residency, financial constraints and family needs, and pursuance of another course or career. Positive experiences of those who dropped out were mostly related to the learning gained and the quality of education, having good teachers and professors, gaining friends, enjoying school activities and having good school facilities. Most of the students who dropped out stated that they had no negative experiences. The few who did state that their negative experiences were due to teachers and professors, school processes, and school facilities. This study showed that reasons for

dropout at Jose Rizal University were mostly related to personal and family factors (change of residency and financial constraints) while school-related factors (quality of education, facilities, teachers and schoolmates) were mostly part of the positive and negative experiences of the students. The results of this study could suggest looking into not only school-related interventions but also into designing programs that could cater to parents and families of students in order to anticipate and possibly prevent future drop-outs.

Keywords: Drop-outs, retention, exit interviews

While to most people, dropping out of school would mean a delay in pursuing higher education, to the society as a whole it could mean a possible reduction of the opportunity to be part of the working sector contributing to the economy. Student drop-outs could impact not just the students dropping out of school but their families, communities and the society as well. Thus, educational institutions are bound by the responsibility of helping students achieve their educational and career goals so that in the future they can contribute to the society (Lund, 2009; Orion, 2014). It is, therefore a, concern of academic administrators to ensure that students enrolled in the school will continue to stay in school until they graduate. However, numerous factors cause students to drop out of school.

Most literature commonly refers to the model of Tinto (1975) on student drop-outs. The central idea in the Tinto's model is integration – that whether students persist or drop out is strongly predicted by their degree of academic integration (grade performance, personal development, enjoying subjects, identification with academic norms and

values and with one's role as a student) and social integration (number of friends, personal interactions with faculty and staff, enjoying the school). While the model initially gained support, subsequent literature supporting it seemed to be weakly consistent. Subsequently, the framework of push, pull and falling out factors was proposed by Jordan et al. and Watt and Roessingh in 1994 (Cited in Doll et al., 2013).

Jordan et al. (1994) explained in the framework that a student is pushed out when adverse situations within the school environment ultimately result in dropout while a student can be pulled out when factors inside the student prevent them from completing school (i.e., financial constraints, family changes, family needs). In the same year (1994), Watt and Roessingh added falling out factors (student gradually increases in behaviors or desires of academic disengagement).

While the different models and frameworks provide an overview of the different factors leading to student drop-out, dominant factors or reasons could still differ in different settings or institutions. Common factors would include school factors (facilities, processes, programs), learning factors include educators, teaching methodologies, classmates) and personal factors include students' personal preferences, financial worries, and family changes (refer to figure 1). Looking into the factors for drop-out at the institution level would allow school administrators to design future interventions to anticipate and prevent future drop-outs among its students.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework for Student Drop-Outs

It was the objective of this study to determine the factors for students dropping out of elementary, high school and college in a particular university. Specifically, the study aimed to determine the reasons for and experiences of the students who dropped out.

METHOD

The study utilized a descriptive cross-sectional study employing review of exit interview forms from elementary, high school and college during the academic years 2014-15, 2015-16 and 2016-17 at Jose Rizal University (JRU). Measures were taken to ensure confidentiality and data privacy. Permission was sought before collection of data, records were not taken out of the school office, identifiers or identifying data were not included in the data encoded, and all electronic records of data were surrendered to the concerned administrative office and deleted from the personal computers of the authors. The research proposal for the study was

submitted, presented and approved by the JRU Research Committee before implementation.

Data from the forms, mainly the reasons as well as positive and negative experiences of students who dropped out, were recorded and encoded verbatim. Encoded data were then analyzed according to themes, and different themes were assigned specific codes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The reasons and experiences (positive and negative) of students who dropped out from elementary, high school and college during academic years 2014-15, 2015-16 and 2016-17 at JRU are summarized as follows:

Table 1
Reasons for Dropping Out

	ELEMEN TARY		HIGH SCHOOL		COLLEGE		TOTAL	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Change of residency	140	48.3	15	19.2	85	24.6	240	33.6
Financial/Family needs	79	27.2	8	10.3	133	38.4	220	30.8
Pursue another course/ career	4	1.4	53	67.9	21	6.1	78	10.9
Decision of parents/guardian	12	4.1	0	0.0	14	4.0	26	3.6
Academic	7	2.4	2	2.6	8	2.3	17	2.4
Migrate/ study abroad	10	3.4	0	0.0	7	2.0	17	2.4
Work reasons	2	0.7	0	0.0	10	2.9	12	1.7
Inability to adjust	1	0.3	0	0.0	3	0.9	4	0.6
Others	33	11.4	0	0.0	18	5.2	51	7.1
None/ No answer	2	0.7	0	0.0	47	13.6	49	6.9
TOTAL	290		78		121		1450	

Table 2
Positive Experiences of Student Drop-Outs

POSITIVE EXPERIENCES	ELEMENTARY		HIGH SCHOOL		COLLEGE		TOTAL	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Learning/quality of education	49	18.0	12	15.4	210	17.3	271	22.3
Teachers/professors	35	12.9	10	12.8	183	15.1	228	18.8
Friends/classmates	24	8.8	17	21.8	182	15.0	223	18.4
Activities	38	14.0	12	15.4	149	12.3	199	16.4
School facilities	14	5.1	10	12.8	136	11.2	160	13.2
Self-improvement	29	10.7	3	3.8	81	6.7	113	9.3
Campus environment/ambience	17	6.3	0	0.0	61	5.0	78	6.4
Academic (passing/excelling)	7	2.6	2	2.6	17	1.4	26	2.1
Enjoyed studying in the school	15	5.5	2	2.6	7	0.6	24	2.0
Staff	3	1.1	0	0.0	18	1.5	21	1.7
Processes	0	0.0	0	0.0	19	1.6	19	1.6
Computer programs	2	0.7	0	0.0	3	0.2	5	0.4
Tuition fee	0	0.0	0	0.0	2	0.2	2	0.2
Internet	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	0.1	1	0.1
Others	7	2.6	10	12.8	28	2.3	45	3.7
None/ no answer	32	11.8	0	0.0	116	9.6	148	12.2
TOTAL	272		78		1213		1563	

Table 3
Negative Experiences of Student Drop-Outs

NEGATIVE EXPERIENCES	ELEMEN TARY		HIGH SCHOOL		COLLEGE		TOTAL	
	N	%	N		N	%	N	%
None	222	76.0	2	2.6	536	49.6	760	52.4
Teacher/professor	10	3.4	2	2.6	93	8.6	105	7.2
School Processes	7	2.4	2	2.6	64	5.9	73	5.0
School facilities	2	0.7	7	9.0	59	5.5	68	4.7
Internet connection	2	0.7	24	30.8	36	3.3	62	4.3
Tuition fee	1	0.3	0	0.0	51	4.7	52	3.6
Security guards	4	1.4	1	1.3	43	4.0	48	3.3
Academic problems	4	1.4	0	0.0	41	3.8	45	3.1
Location/Proximity to residence/transportation	16	5.5	11	14.1	15	1.4	42	2.9
Staff	1	0.3	0	0.0	32	3.0	33	2.3
ID problems	4	1.4	5	6.4	23	2.1	32	2.2
Uniform	0	0.0	0	0.0	28	2.6	28	1.9
Friends/classmates/Bullying	0	0.0	0	0.0	19	1.8	19	1.3
Canteen	4	1.4	0	0.0	5	0.5	9	0.6
Activities	0	0.0	0	0.0	8	0.7	8	0.6
Lack of section	1	0.3	2	2.6	2	0.2	5	0.3
Smoking in certain areas	0	0.0	0	0.0	3	0.3	3	0.2
Others	14	0.3	22	28.2	22	2.0	58	4.0
TOTAL	292		78		1080		1450	

A majority of the reasons for dropping out included change of residence, financial/ family needs and pursuance of another course or career. Change of residence, proximity to the school and transportation problems were stated in 33.6% of the responses and included transferring to another city (stated as "*lilipat ng bahay*", *home transfer*), returning to the hometown in the province (stated as "*going back to the province*", "*school far from permanent residence*") and transfer of job of parents of which locations were farther from the school. Financial constraints and family needs included the inability to pay or afford tuition fees were

simply stated as “*money matter, financial problem, tuition, family problem/ financial,*” and were stated in 30.8% of the responses. Pursuance of another course or career (especially for college students) in 10.9% of the responses were stated as “*wanted to experience something new, wanted to be good in certain area, take a different course*” and thus included transferring to another school or course which the students believed would allow them to pursue their future career and dreams. Other reasons cited were: the decision of parents/ guardians, failing in school, migration, work reasons (mostly for college) and inability to adjust. It could be observed that the typical reasons stated could be categorized as pull out factors or that the students who dropped out were mostly pulled out by personal factors such as family changes (particularly in residence) and family needs (mainly financial).

Positive experiences of the students were mostly related to learning a lot, getting a quality education and the teaching methodologies employed (22.3%). Having excellent and considerate teachers and professors (18.8%), gaining friends and having nice classmates (18.4%), school activities (16.4%) and school facilities (13.2%) including library facilities were also common positive experiences among those who dropped out. Other positive experiences included the campus environment, excelling academically, enjoying studying, the staff, school processes, computer programs, tuition fee and internet connection. These positive experiences could somehow be categorized under Tinto’s model which included academic integration (learning, academic performance) and social integration (gaining friends, enjoying studying) as factors for students’ retention and drop-out.

Most of those who dropped out did not have any negative experiences (52.4%) as stated by the response of *none* or *not applicable* to negative experiences. A few of those with negative experiences were related to teachers/professors and school processes. Negative experiences with teachers/professors included having teachers or professors who were always absent/late/difficult to contact and inconsiderate and stated as

“very strict professor, the teacher was always late, cannot be contacted, gave very low grades”, and were found in 7.2% of the responses. Inefficient school processes such as enrolling and getting grades stated as *“registrar processes not efficient, enrollment processes and papers, getting a transcript, getting a grade”* were cited in 5.4% of negative experiences. Other negative experiences were related to school facilities, internet connection, tuition fee, strict security guards, academic problems, transportation/ going to school, dealing with staff, identification card problems and uniform preferences. Bullying stated as *“I was bullied, I have been bullied, bullying, bully/ bullying schoolmates”* was found in 1.1% of the responses in negative experiences. These experiences are related to push out factors in the framework of Jordan et al. which explained that school factors and consequences could have pushed out the students from the school.

The common reasons (change in residence, financial constraints) as well as positive experiences (quality of education, having good teachers, gaining friends) and negative experiences (mostly none) of students from elementary, high school and college at Jose Rizal University from 2014-17 were consistent with the previous studies stating academic integration and social integration (Tinto, 1975) and push and pull factors (Jordan et al, 1994) and fall-out factors (Watt and Roessingh, 1994) as factors affecting student dropouts.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study found that a change of residence and financial constraints were the common reasons for dropping out of the institution. It also revealed that having a quality education, excellent teachers and gaining friends were common positive experiences among students who dropped out of elementary, high school and college of Jose Rizal University from 2014 to 2017. Given the results of the study, it is recommended that the institution looks into interventions to improve the

school factors that could prevent students from being pushed out of school. These interventions may include the provision of additional facilities such as students' dormitory and official school bus especially for students who live far from the school. Distance learning activities should also be maximized from elementary, high school and college students. Blended learning and online courses may also be offered to college students to provide them with more options.

Furthermore, programs should be designed for parents and families of students in order to prevent personal and familial factors from pulling students out of the school. These interventions for parents and families may include educational programs on financial literacy and entrepreneurship as well as personal and career development and networking opportunities that could gear towards preventing or alleviating financial needs among families of students. These recommendations and other interventions may be done not just to prevent but also to anticipate future drop-outs so that the institution can eventually launch students to be productive members of the society without any delay.

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